

32 step, RNA-Editing sites being mistaken for DNA variants, and inaccurate variants being called
33 around RNA splice junctions (Sheng et al., 2016; Martín-Alonso, Frutos-Beltrán, & Menéndez-
34 Arias, 2021; Gott & Emeson, 2000; Brouard et al., 2019; Deelen et al., 2015; Rogier et al., 2018).
35 This pipeline includes data processing steps to mitigate the number of false variant calls.

36 We present a pipeline of suggested software and custom scripts to call novel variants in a
37 highly inbred species (Supplementary Figure S1). Here, we describe the modifications to deal with
38 a lack of paired tissue samples or known sets of variants and the nature of a highly homozygous
39 species.

40

41 **2. Pipeline Description**

42 *2.1. Aligning reads*

43 Quality-controlled RNA-Sequencing fastq reads from samples exposed to either control or
44 treatment conditions are first aligned with STAR in 2-pass mode to ensure splice junctions are
45 carefully examined. This limits false variant calls surrounding RNA splice junctions which can be
46 more frequent due to increased difficulty mapping RNA-Seq reads (Sheng et al., 2016; Brouard,
47 Schenkel, Marete, & Bissonnette, 2019).

48

49 *2.2 Pre-processing for variant calling*

50 The first pre-processing step for variant calling uses SplitNCigarReads on aligned reads.
51 SplitNCigarReads takes reads encompassing a splice site and separates the read into the sequence
52 before and after splice sites. SplitNCigarReads cuts nucleotides that are mapped to the intronic
53 region (Van der Auwera, O'Connor, & Safari, 2020). This is a standard step in other variant calling
54 pipelines which work with RNA-Seq data (Gonorazky et al., 2019).

55 The next pre-processing step is base quality score recalibration (Van der Auwera et al., 2020).
56 Base quality scores are a certainty estimate for each base (Van der Auwera et al., 2020). However,
57 known error sources can reduce their accuracy. Our pipeline includes two GATK tools to readjust
58 inaccurate quality scores, BaseRecalibrator and ApplyBQSR. These standardly used tools for
59 variant calling produce a new alignment file with adjusted base quality scores to improve accuracy
60 (Ebbert et al., 2016).

61

62 *2.3 Identifying inherited mutations to create an Ultimate Panel of Normals*

63 We generate an Ultimate Panel of Normals (PON) to separate existing polymorphic sites that
64 are inherited from non-inherited variants identified across samples. Our pipeline combines two
65 approaches to generate the Ultimate PON without requiring a prior list of known polymorphic sites
66 from common variants. First, HaplotypeCaller is used in joint genotyping mode to call variants
67 (Poplin et al., 2017). The “heterozygosity” parameter should be set to a low value for highly inbred
68 species (for example, when applied to *Arabidopsis thaliana*, we used a value of 0.0001).
69 GenomicsDBImport combines each sample’s variant call file (VCF) and GenotypeGVCFs does
70 the final joint genotyping (Van der Auwera et al., 2020). Joint genotyping tags shared mutations
71 among the group of samples. Highly inbred species are likely to share most of their inherited
72 variants, so the list of mutations from HaplotypeCaller will include these shared mutations.

73 A second set of likely inherited mutations is created using Mutect2 in “tumor-only” mode. For
74 inbred species, the “maximum number of haplotypes” parameter is set to a low number (when
75 applied to *Arabidopsis*, we used a value of 2). The VCFs produced by Mutect2 are combined using
76 GenomicsDBImport and a PON is created using CreateSomaticPanelofNormals (Van der Auwera
77 et al., 2020).

78 To combine the variants identified by HaplotypeCaller and Mutect2, variants called by either
79 tool, and present in at least three samples, are considered likely inherited and used to compose the
80 Ultimate PON. This Ultimate PON is used as the known set of polymorphic sites for
81 BaseRecalibrator and the PON for Mutect2.

82

83 *2.4 Variant calling*

84 Popular variant calling tools tend to focus on calling hereditary mutations (Poplin et al., 2017).
85 However, we are interested in identifying variants that may have occurred due to environmental
86 conditions. Therefore, we used GATK’s Mutect2 in tumor-only mode to call variants. Mutect2
87 compares nucleotides to a reference genome and uses a PON to distinguish common mutations
88 present in all samples (Van der Auwera et al., 2020). Our pipeline provides the Ultimate PON (2.3)
89 for Mutect2 to distinguish common SNPs among the samples that differ from the reference
90 genome.

91

92 *2.5 Variant filtering*

93 Variant filtration is a necessary quality control step to help combat false variant calls (Van der
94 Auwera et al., 2020). We incorporated hard filters, deduplication, the removal of variants in
95 difficult to sequence reads, and filtering based on gene expression into this pipeline to reduce false
96 variants.

97

98 *2.5.1 Hard filtering*

99 Hard filters remove variants for specified reasons like low read depth or low mapping quality
100 (Van der Auwera et al., 2020) and removes tagged mutations identified in the Ultimate PON
101 created in 2.3. This pipeline uses GATK's VariantFiltration for hard filtering (Van der Auwera et
102 al., 2020).

103

104 *2.5.2 Deduplication*

105 Normally, deduplication is done after reads are aligned to the genome and before variant
106 calling to minimize PCR duplication error (Ebbert et al., 2016; Sayols, Scherzinger, & Klein,
107 2016). This could result in variants not being called by Mutect2 or being filtered out due to low
108 read depth or support, because deduplication risks real biological duplicate reads not being
109 examined for potential variants (Sayols et al., 2016). Our pipeline moves deduplication to after
110 variant calling (Supplementary Figure S2). A custom script judges variants by the number of
111 unique reads supporting them ([https://github.com/montana-knight/Calling-Induced-Variants-
112 with-RNA-Seq-Data/tree/master/step4/scripts/deduplication](https://github.com/montana-knight/Calling-Induced-Variants-with-RNA-Seq-Data/tree/master/step4/scripts/deduplication)). If a variant is only found in identical
113 reads mapping to the same location with no mismatches, then it is considered a PCR duplicate and
114 is filtered out. Our variant-centric deduplication method retains reads with different variants even
115 if they would otherwise be marked as duplicates.

116

117 *2.5.3 Removal of Difficult to Sequence Reads*

118 Variants in difficult to sequence reads were removed using a custom script in the pipeline
119 ([https://github.com/montana-knight/Calling-Induced-Variants-with-RNA-Seq-
120 Data/blob/master/step4/scripts/remove_tricky_reads.R](https://github.com/montana-knight/Calling-Induced-Variants-with-RNA-Seq-Data/blob/master/step4/scripts/remove_tricky_reads.R)). The pipeline filters out mutations at the
121 end of a trinucleotide sequence made up of a single nucleotide (e.g., AAA). Although these
122 difficult regions are prone to sequencing error, they are also difficult regions for native DNA

123 polymerase, so this conservative approach may remove real variants (Kroutil, Register, Bebenek,
124 & Kunkel, 1996).

125

126 *2.5.4 Accounting for gene expression*

127 We use a custom script to remove variants in lowly expressed genes (fewer than 10 counts per
128 gene). This step is redundant if variants with read depths lower than 10 were already filtered out.
129 To ensure differential expression among treatment groups does not influence results, the script
130 only keeps variants from genes expressed in all samples ([https://github.com/montana-
131 knight/Calling-Induced-Variants-with-RNA-Seq-
132 Data/blob/master/step4/scripts/filter_by_expression.R](https://github.com/montana-knight/Calling-Induced-Variants-with-RNA-Seq-Data/blob/master/step4/scripts/filter_by_expression.R)).

133

134 **3. Data analysis**

135 The output of this pipeline are the final filtered variant call files. These filtered variants can be
136 further examined. Due to the high false positive nature of identifying variants using RNA-Seq
137 data, we recommend a focus on analyzing the number of variants identified, along with variant
138 composition and possibly location, rather than focusing on variant annotation.

139

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